

Technology of Organizing Pedagogical Practice in Preparing Future Teachers for Professional Activity

Djuraboyev Maqsudbek Karimbek ugli

Teacher of the "Computer Engineering" department of Andijan State University

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the role and importance of pedagogical practice in preparing future teachers for professional activities. It highlights the possibilities of testing theoretical knowledge in practice, developing professional skills, and using modern technologies and best practices through pedagogical practice. The article also discusses the problems that may be encountered in the process of pedagogical practice and ways to solve them. This research serves to increase the professional training of future teachers and improve the quality of education.

Keywords: pedagogical practice, professional training, modern technologies, best practices, teacher training, quality of education.

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogical practice is essential in preparing future teachers for professional activities. Through pedagogical practice, future teachers will have the opportunity to test their theoretical knowledge in practice, improve their professional skills, and engage in the teaching process in a real educational environment. This process serves the personal and professional development of future teachers in their specialty, thoroughly prepares them for their future professional activities.

The technology of pedagogical practice is a significant component of the modern educational process. Its effective organization allows to form pedagogical skills of future teachers, plan lessons and effectively start the process of communication with students.

RELEVANCE OF THE TOPIC

The role of pedagogical practice in the preparation of future teachers for professional activity is of urgent importance. In order to provide high-quality education to students in the modern education process, teachers are required to have excellent not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills. Through pedagogical practice, future teachers will have the opportunity to gain experience in a real classroom environment in their specialty, to study in depth various facets of the educational process. Today, rapid changes in the education system, technological development and the needs of students show that pedagogical practice requires more effective and innovative approaches. Organization of pedagogical practice using modern technologies such as distance education, virtual reality, interactive educational tools helps to increase the quality of education. Herewith, pedagogical practice greatly contributes to the professional and personal development of future teachers and allows them to thoroughly prepare for their future professional activities. The relevance of this process is that it serves to improve the quality of

the teaching profession and creates a solid foundation for the development of the educational system. Also, through pedagogical practice, teachers acquire the skills to correctly understand the needs of students and implement an individual approach to them, which helps to make the educational process more effective and humane.

A BRIEF ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ON THE TOPIC

Scientific research on pedagogical practice was conducted by many pedagogues and scientists. These studies are mainly aimed at studying the importance of pedagogical practice in preparing future teachers for professional activities. The following main aspects were analyzed in the studies:

Integration of theory and practice: Many scientific studies emphasize that pedagogical practice allows future teachers to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. For example, in educational programs, knowledge acquired through theoretical lessons is applied and strengthened in real classroom conditions. The pedagogical effectiveness of this process has been widely considered by researchers, and it has been proven how significant practical experience is for teachers.

Development of professional competences: Studies have shown that pedagogical practice has a great role in the improvement of professional skills of future teachers. In the process of practice, teachers develop essential skills such as effective communication with students, lesson planning and management, and the use of educational tools. That is why the role of pedagogic practice in professional training has been in constant attention in scientific research. There are many scientific articles about the integration of modern technologies into pedagogical practice. In these studies, the effectiveness of online learning platforms, interactive tools, gamification, and virtual reality in the process of teacher training has been investigated. Researchers have deeply analyzed the impact of technologies on innovative approaches in the pedagogical process and the increase in the quality of education. The role of the reflective approach in the professional development of future teachers is studied separately in scientific sources. Reflective practice gives future teachers the opportunity to analyze their activities, identify mistakes and make changes. Through this, it is possible to constantly improve pedagogical skills. Many scientific studies have shown the advantages of introducing advanced pedagogical methods into pedagogical practice. Methods such as project-based learning, mentoring programs, case studies, and working in small groups have been evaluated as effective methods for professional development of teachers.

The analysis of the **article's scientific novelty** is reflected in the following factors: The article examines methods of effective organization of the pedagogical process using new, innovative technologies. This situation presents new scientific approaches to the role of educational technologies and their integration in the process of teacher training.

In this article new approaches to the implementation of information and communication technologies into the educational process have been analyzed. In this direction, new theoretical and practical recommendations on the use of information technologies in education have been developed.

The article includes modern approaches to strengthening the psychological preparation of teachers. On this subject, the methods of increasing students' motivation and ensuring psychological flexibility are included as innovations.

Research on the organization of practical exercises and training in a new form in the preparation of future teachers is considered a scientific novelty of the article. In this direction, new methodological methods aimed at self-development and effective communication with students are proposed for future teachers.

THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Is to develop methods of effective use of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the process of training future teachers and to achieve an increase in the professional competence of teachers through their integration into the educational process.

THE OBJECT OF RESEARCH

Is the use of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the process of training future teachers and the process of integration into the educational process. The research on this object will examine the combination of pedagogical processes with modern technologies, the use of effective methods of improving the qualifications of teachers, and the pedagogical conditions in this process.

MAIN PART

Lesson planning is an important part of pedagogical practice and helps future teachers to effectively organize the educational process. By creating a lesson plan, the teacher clearly defines educational goals, chooses teaching methods and uses various methods to assess the level of knowledge of students. Proper planning increases the effectiveness of the lesson and ensures active participation of students.

Also, Pedagogical practice teaches future teachers how to effectively communicate with students. Determining the needs of students, taking into account their interests and actively involving them in the educational process are the main aspects of pedagogical communication. Through effective communication with students during practice, future teachers will have the opportunity to increase their self-confidence, support in the educational process, and strengthen the motivation of students.

The use of modern technologies in the organization of pedagogical practice plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. The following modern technologies can be widely used in the training of future teachers:

- 1. Distance and online platforms:** The use of distance learning platforms, such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams or Google Meet in the organization of pedagogical practice makes the practice more convenient. Through these tools, future teachers will develop the skills to conduct online classes, communicate with students remotely, and manage the lesson process.
- 2. Virtual reality (VR) and simulations:** With the help of VR technology, future teachers can experience the classroom environment virtually. This will help them prepare in advance for situations they may encounter in the real classroom. Practicing the teaching process through simulations enhances the experience of future teachers.
- 3. Interactive learning tools:** With the help of interactive whiteboards, digital presentation tools and educational software, future teachers can make their lessons more interesting and effective. These technologies allow to attract the attention of students and make the lesson materials more understandable.
- 4. Electronic portfolios:** With the help of electronic portfolios, future teachers can document their pedagogical activities and monitor their changes. This will help them to analyze their work and draw important conclusions for professional development.
- 5. Gamification:** By adding elements of gamification to the educational process, it is possible to increase the motivation of future teachers and develop their pedagogical skills. Through this method, students are more actively involved in the learning process, as a result, the practical process becomes more interesting and effective.

- 6. Educational analytics and feedback technologies:** Teachers can track student activity and mastery with the help of educational analytics. These technologies help to determine which topics students are good at and which ones they are struggling with. Also, future teachers will have the opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of their lessons through rapid feedback technologies.

These modern technologies make the process of organizing pedagogical practice effective, interesting and innovative. With the help of these technologies, future teachers will improve their professional skills and be ready for the real educational process.

In the process of pedagogical practice, future teachers may face various problems. It is necessary to identify these problems and create effective strategies to solve them:

- 1. Inadequate preparation for practice:** In many cases, it is observed that future teachers are theoretically well prepared for practice, but they are not sufficiently prepared practically. To prevent this, it is necessary to enrich theoretical knowledge with practical exercises, to simulate situations in the classroom, and to conduct small group exercises.
- 2. Lack of mentoring support:** Future teachers may be deprived of support and enough abutment of mentors during pedagogical practice. To solve this problem, it is necessary to train mentors and give them instructions on how to help future teachers. Systematic organization of the mentoring process and regular communication with teachers is required.
- 3. Difficulties in communicating with students:** Future teachers may face difficulties in communicating effectively with students. To prevent such situations, it will be useful to organize trainings and seminars aimed at developing communication skills, as well as practicing communication skills through role-playing games and simulations.
- 4. Stress and psychological difficulties:** During the pedagogical practice, future teachers may be under stress and psychological pressure. In order to overcome this situation, it is necessary to establish psychological support and counseling services, to organize training on stress management technics and emotional intelligence development.
- 5. Lack of technical resources:** There may be a problem of non-availability of necessary technical tools or limited access to them in practice areas. To solve this problem, it is necessary to provide technical resources, as well as to train future teachers in advance to use them.
- 6. Lack of motivation:** Some future teachers may suffer from lack of motivation during pedagogical practice. To overcome this situation, it is necessary to increase motivation by introducing gamification elements, using incentive systems and public recognition of student achievements.

By solving these problems, it is possible to make the process of pedagogical practice more effective and interesting, and to improve the professional training of future teachers. This, in turn, serves to improve the quality of the educational process

It is important to use best practices to improve the professional training of future teachers. Here are some best practices that can be applied in pedagogical practice:

- 1. Project-based learning:** Through project-based learning, prospective teachers empower students to solve problems, create projects, and implement them. This method helps to develop creativity and independent thinking skills of teachers in the educational process.
- 2. Mentoring Programs:** Through mentoring programs, experienced teachers mentor, give advice, and support prospective teachers. This process ensures self-confidence and professional growth of future teachers.

3. **Reflective practice:** Reflective practice creates an opportunity to analyze the pedagogical activity of teachers and self-evaluate. Through this method, they identify shortcomings in their work, draw conclusions from them, and try to improve their work in the future.
4. **Working in small groups:** By working in small groups, future teachers develop the skills to create a collaborative classroom environment and communicate effectively with students. This approach will increase the activity and participation of students in the educational process.
5. **Situation Analysis:** Using the method of situation analysis allows future teachers to analyze real-life situations, find solutions to them, and develop decision-making skills. Through this method, they will be ready to make the right decision in different pedagogical situations.
6. **Multicultural Education:** Multicultural education teaches prospective teachers how to teach with the needs of diverse cultural groups in mind. This experience helps them to ensure inclusiveness in the educational process and form an individual approach to each student.

By applying these best practices, it is possible to increase the professional training of future teachers, their success in the educational process, and the quality of education.

Technologies for organizing pedagogical practice are of great importance in preparing future teachers for professional activity. The following steps can be developed to effectively implement this process:

1. **Practice planning:** In order to successfully organize a pedagogical practice, it is important to plan it in advance. At this stage, goals and tasks corresponding to the curriculum are defined, relations with partner educational institutions are established, and students are prepared for practice.
2. **Theoretical and practical training:** In order to prepare future teachers for practice, it is necessary to deepen theoretical knowledge and develop professional skills. At this stage, the teacher teaches students teaching methods, learning process management technologies, and the basic rules of working with the class.
3. **Internship:** At this stage, student teachers will have direct teaching experience in educational institutions. They learn to make lesson plans, prepare didactic materials and manage the educational process. At this stage, mentor teachers help students and evaluate their work.
4. **Analysis and reflection:** At the end of the internship, student teachers analyze their activities and discuss their results with mentors. This stage is important for students to identify their strengths and weaknesses, to understand how to improve it in the future.
5. **Reflection and Evaluation:** Prospective teachers reflect on their professional development by analyzing and evaluating their practicum experiences. Reflection helps to deeply analyze the problems encountered in practice and find solutions to them.
6. **Use of information technologies:** Information technologies play an important role in modern education. Therefore, the use of online resources, digital platforms and distance learning tools in the organization of pedagogical practice allows students to organize innovative lessons.

Pedagogical practice is an important process in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities, it provides testing of theoretical knowledge in practice, development of professional skills and gaining experience in a real educational environment. Effective organization of this practice provides teachers with skills in lesson planning, effective

communication with students, and management of the educational process.

Modern technologies, such as distance learning platforms, virtual reality and simulations, interactive educational tools and gamification help make the practice process effective and interesting. Also, best practices such as mentoring programs, reflective practice, and working in small groups contribute greatly to the professional development of future teachers.

It is necessary to develop effective strategies to solve the problems encountered during the practice. These strategies include measures such as combining theoretical and practical training, using mentoring support, and overcoming stress and technical difficulties. It is possible to thoroughly prepare teachers for professional activity by planning pedagogical practice, theoretical and practical training, analysis and reflection processes.

CONCLUSIONS

- The role of pedagogical practice in preparing future teachers for professional activity is very important. They will have the opportunity not only to test their theoretical knowledge in practice, but also to improve their professional skills.
- In the modern educational process, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical practice by using distance education, virtual reality and interactive tools. This helps teachers to feel comfortable in the educational process.
- Pedagogical practice makes it possible to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. This helps to strengthen teachers' knowledge and increase practical experience.
- In the process of pedagogical practice, future teachers will have the opportunity to develop the skills of effective communication with students, planning and management of lessons. These skills prepare teachers for their future careers.
- Reflective activities of teachers allow to analyze their activities, identify shortcomings and make changes. This process helps to constantly develop pedagogical skills.
- The introduction of advanced pedagogical methods and innovative approaches is essential in improving the professional training of future teachers. Methods such as project-based training, mentoring programs, and gamification serve to make the educational process interesting and effective.
- It is necessary to develop effective strategies to solve the problems faced by teachers in the process of pedagogical practice. Eliminating problems such as preparation for practice, insufficient mentoring support, difficulties in communication with students is important for the successful work of teachers.
- It is important to use innovative and best practices to improve the professional training of future teachers. It helps to effectively communicate with students in the learning process, improve the quality of education and help teachers in self-development.

Offers:

- It is necessary to develop programs that combine theoretical knowledge and practical experience of teachers. It provides students with hands-on experience and prepares them for practice.
- We offer the use of distance learning platforms, virtual classes and other innovative technologies for teachers. This helps to make the educational process convenient and effective.
- It is necessary to support new teachers by creating mentoring programs between experienced teachers and novice teachers and allow them to learn practical experience.

- It is recommended to hold seminars and trainings for teachers aimed at developing reflective activities. This process helps teachers analyze their experiences.
- It is necessary to organize training for teachers aimed at developing the skills of planning, managing lessons and effective communication with students.
- Teachers are invited to develop and present strategies for effective communication with students, as well as conduct seminars aimed at improving communication skills.
- In order for teachers to learn problem-solving strategies, it is recommended to conduct training aimed at identifying and eliminating problems during practice.
- Teachers should introduce mechanisms for collecting opinions and comments from students in order to further improve their work. This helps to continuously improve the educational process.
- It is necessary to study and introduce international experiences into the educational system of Uzbekistan, which will help the professional development of teachers and increase the quality of education.
- It is recommended to organize awards and contests to introduce innovative approaches and encourage teachers who have achieved success in pedagogical practice.

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